

Impact of Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT) on Older Adults with Obsessive Compulsive Disorder (OCD) in Abuja Metropolitan Area Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study focuses on the impact of the acceptance and commitment therapy (ACT) on older adults with obsessive compulsive disorder (OCD) in Abuja metropolitan area Nigeria. Obsessive-Compulsive Disorder (OCD) is a condition consisting of disturbing mental obsessions in which the person is excessively worried or unwanted thoughts or impulses are constantly repeated, and compulsions, which are repetitive behaviours. Compulsions manifest themselves as behaviours such as repeating certain rules, patterns or rituals, checking or cleaning a certain number of times. Individuals with OCD experience serious problems in their daily lives because of these thoughts and behaviours. Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT) is a type of psychotherapy that focuses on the person's inner experiences as part of the cognitive behavioural therapy approach. ACT aims to help the person to accept disturbing thoughts, feelings and physical sensations quietly and with understanding, and to cope with them in a more flexible way. Research shows that ACT is effective in reducing OCD symptoms and is therefore considered as an effective therapy option in the treatment of OCD. Furthermore, it focus on how the integration and combination of ACT with other treatment modalities can benefit in the field of OCD treatment. In this way, more effective and personalised methods can be developed in the treatment of OCD patients. A single case design was used in five older adults with obsessive compulsive disorder. Results suggested the significant decreases in all measures in five older patients and these results maintained at 1-month follow up. Process of treatment and results from this study suggest that Acceptance and Commitment Therapy can be effective intervention for difficult thoughts, feelings, and behaviors seen in OCD. The results of meta-analysis on the effect of ACT alone showed that ACT had a better effect on OCD than other treatment methods ($MD = -3.76$, $Z = 4.41$, $P \leq 0.05$). Meta-analysis results of ACT combined SSRIs therapy showed that ACT combined therapy was better than SSRIs alone ($MD = 7.18$, $Z = 6.59$, $P \leq 0.05$). The study concluded that acceptance commitment therapy can effectively treat OCD.

Keywords: *Impact, Acceptance, Commitment, Therapy, Older, Adults, Obsessive, Compulsive, Disorder, Nigeria*

INTRODUCTION

Acceptance and commitment therapy (ACT, typically pronounced as the word "act") is a form of psychotherapy, as well as a branch of clinical behavior analysis. It is an empirically-based psychological intervention that uses acceptance and mindfulness strategies along with commitment and behavior-change strategies to increase psychological flexibility. This approach was first called *comprehensive distancing*. Steven C. Hayes developed it around 1982 to integrate features of cognitive therapy and behavior analysis, especially behavior analytic data on the often negative effects of verbal rules and how they might be ameliorated. ACT protocols vary with the target behavior and the setting. For example, in behavioral health, a brief version of ACT is *focused acceptance and commitment therapy* (FACT). The goal of ACT is not to eliminate difficult feelings but to be present with what life brings and to "move toward valued behavior". Acceptance and commitment therapy invites people to open up to unpleasant feelings, not to overreact to them, and not to avoid situations that cause them. Its therapeutic effect aims to be a positive spiral, in which more understanding of one's emotions leads to a better understanding of the truth. In ACT, "truth" is measured through the concept of "workability", or what works to take another step toward what matters (e.g., values, meaning).

In 2006, only about 30 randomized clinical trials and controlled time series evaluating ACT were known, in 2011 the number had doubled to more than 60 ACT randomized controlled trials, and in 2023 there were more than 1,000 randomized controlled trials of ACT worldwide. A 2008 meta-analysis concluded that the evidence was still too limited for ACT to be considered a supported treatment. A 2009 meta-analysis found that ACT was more effective than placebo and "treatment as usual" for most problems. A 2012 meta-analysis was more positive and reported that ACT outperformed CBT, except for treating depression and anxiety. A 2015 review found that ACT was better than placebo and typical treatment for anxiety disorders, depression, and addiction. Its effectiveness was similar to traditional treatments like cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT). The authors also noted that research methodologies had improved since the studies described in the 2008 meta-analysis.

In 2020, a review of meta-analyses examined 20 meta-analyses that included 133 studies and 12,477 participants. The authors concluded ACT is efficacious for all conditions examined, including anxiety, depression, substance use, pain, and transdiagnostic groups. Results also showed that ACT was generally superior to inactive controls, treatment as usual, and most active intervention conditions. In 2020–2021, after three RCTs of ACT by the World Health Organization (WHO), WHO released an ACT-based self-help course Self-Help Plus (SH+) for "groups of up to 30 people who have lived through or are living through adversity". As of July 2023, there are six RCTs of Self-Help Plus.

In 2022, a systematic review of meta-analyses about interventions for depressive symptoms in people living with chronic pain concluded "Acceptance and commitment therapy for general chronic pain, and fluoxetine and web-based psychotherapy for fibromyalgia showed the most robust effects and can be prioritized for implementation in clinical practice". Recent studies conducted about ACT have provided some satisfactory results and logical reasons for using ACT

in clinical activity, in particular, working with the patients affected by anxiety disorders. In area of the obsession, Twohig, Hayes and Masuda studied ACT as a therapy of OCD for 4 patients. The results showed nearly complete reduction of compulsions for all the participants at the end of the therapy; together with reductions in the standard scales of obsession, anxiety, depression and preventing from an experience which also continued for a three-month follow-up period. In addition, regarding the scales of the therapy's process, all the participants showed that they have a higher tendency toward experiencing obsessive thoughts, while, they believe less in obsessive thoughts in terms of the result of therapy. In this regard, the effectiveness of an ACT treatment program consisting of 10 sessions without inside-the-session exposure was studied and assessed on 5 patients affected by obsessive compulsive disorder. (Cheng, Darren; Lai, Ka Sing Paris 2022)

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Conceptual Framework

According to Hayes' classification, the first wave, behaviour therapy, commenced in the 1920s based on Pavlov's classical (respondent) conditioning and operant conditioning that was correlated to reinforcing consequences. The second wave emerged in the 1970s and included cognition in the form of irrational beliefs, dysfunctional attitudes or depressogenic attributions. In the late 1980s empirical limitations and philosophical misgivings of the second wave gave rise to Steven Hayes' ACT theory which modified the focus of abnormal behaviour away from the content or form towards the context in which it occurs. People's rigid ideas about themselves, their lack of focus on what is important in their life, and their struggle to change sensations, feelings or thoughts that are troublesome only serve to create greater distress. (Cookson, Camilla; Luzon, Olga; Newland, John; Kingston, Jessica 2020).

Values in mainstream psychology

In psychology, the idea of human values and their importance is associated primarily with the humanistic movement, according to which people are motivated by psychological growth and self-direction and ultimately strive for the fullest realization or actualization of their human potential. Perhaps the best known humanistic psychologist is Carl Rogers, who regarded the pursuit of values as key to actualization and psychological health. Rogers (1964) distinguished between conceived values (verbal expressions of preference) and operative values (actual behavior) and suggested that much of human suffering resulted from discrepancies between these two, as in the case of a person stating a preference for a particular pursuit but not spending any time actually engaged in it. He developed client-centered therapy (later known as person-centered therapy), with the intention of guiding clients to live more congruently with their conceptualized values and hence live more fulfilling and psychologically healthy lives (Rogers 1964).

Perhaps the main problem with the humanistic approach, from a broadly scientific perspective, is the lack of cumulative empirical evidence for its theoretical statements, whether with regard to values or other concepts. This weakness in terms of its scientific underpinning is perhaps not surprising, because humanism was developed in part as a reaction against behaviorism and scientific psychology more generally (Rogers & Skinner, 1956). Accordingly, humanists regarded

concepts such as determinism and objectivity as irrelevant and perhaps even as antithetical to dealing with the human condition. From the current perspective, this is a serious weakness. (Dozois, David, Beck, Aaron 2011).

Recent outgrowths of the humanistic movement have become more empirically oriented. Motivational interviewing (MI; Miller, 1983), for instance, is a modern humanistic approach with a Rogerian focus on values–behavior consistency that has accumulated a good deal of empirical evidence in its favor as a treatment and as an adjunct to increase the effectiveness of other cognitive behavioral methods (e.g., Arkowitz, Westra, Miller, & Rollnick, 2008). Miller and Rollnick (2002) describe MI as a process in which clients come to be motivated to behave in a more values-congruent manner by identifying the higher personal values that are salient to any particular situation. MI therapists facilitate therapeutic change by helping clients to examine barriers to living values-congruent lives. For example, therapists help them to recognize the negative consequences of their current behavior, or the relevance of a value to a specific behavioral choice. MI therapists also work to help clients take responsibility for their behavior when clients blame an illness, diagnosis, label (“I am an alcoholic”), or a thought (“I just can’t handle this anxiety”) for the fact that they are not living values-congruent lives. *Gloster, Andrew, Walder, Noemi; Levin, Michael, (Twohig, Michael, Karekla, Maria 2020).*

Although positive psychologists such as Sheldon have espoused the importance of providing empirical evidence as support for theoretical statements, positive psychology has other weaknesses that it shares with the older humanist tradition. For example, positive psychology employs terms such as *character, potential, striving, and personal control* that remain relatively poorly specified at the level of basic behavioral processes. The absence of such specification is problematic because it entails a failure to achieve prediction and influence of behavior and hence to provide a basis for psychological interventions that might change a person's behavior in accordance with theoretical goals. Thus, although analyses provided by positive psychologists and humanists point the way towards potentially important variables such as values, the lack of behavioral precision in the definition of their terms means that specification of effective practical interventions on the basis of these analyses is much less likely. Having briefly examined some well-known mainstream approaches to values, and described problems with these from a scientific behavioral perspective, we turn next to an examination of values in cognitive behavior therapy, the clinical tradition with which ACT is perhaps most closely associated. (Harris, Russ 2006).

Cognitive behavioural therapy and values

The emergence of values as a specific focus of interest in cognitive behavior therapy (CBT) is a relatively recent phenomenon. It may be argued that several forms of CBT do seek to effect changes in line with the ACT conceptualization of values, but interventions do not typically conceptualize such changes as linked to personal values and do not target such changes as mediators of change or as outcomes. Traditionally (although there is great variation among CBT therapies), these therapies have been designed to treat sets of symptoms defined by the *Diagnostic*

and *Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders* (American Psychiatric Association, 2000), and many psychological treatments have focused primarily on ameliorating symptoms. For example, treatment for depression has focused on alleviating feelings of depression by reducing automatic thoughts (e.g., Beck, Rush, Shaw, & Emery, 1979), and treatment for phobias has focused on exposing clients to feared stimuli until the fear response does not occur (e.g., Barlow, 2001). Such treatments, which have used the statistically significant reduction of depression or anxiety as the primary metric of success, are typical of traditional CBT. (*Hassert, Derrick, Kelly, Amanda, Pritchard, Joshua, Cautilli, Joseph 2022*)

However, one feature of these diagnoses and psychological problems has remained largely overlooked as CBT has become increasingly refined; that feature is negative impact on quality of life. To be diagnosed as a psychological disorder, a problem must cause an individual some functional impairment or clinically significant distress. However, the presence of significant psychological distress or impairment also invariably influences the person's ability to live a fulfilling life. Some CBT practitioners focus only on amelioration of symptoms, but others practice psychotherapy in line with this focus on functional impairment, and as such have begun to attend to quality of life in their practice, and some have also begun to include measures to assess changes in this variable following intervention. (*Hofmann, Stefan, Asmundson, Gordon J.G. 2008*).

A diversity of measures for this purpose had already been developed in the fields of medicine and health psychology (e.g., Anderson & Burckhardt, 1999; Diener, Emmons, & Larsen, 1985; Frisch, Clark, & Rouse, 2005; World Health Organization, 1995); thus, clinical psychologists have turned to these ready-made instruments for use in their work. However, from the current perspective, these instruments are missing something very important; namely, any link to a theory that allows the manipulation of important psychological or environmental variables in order to effect change. Nevertheless, the lack of such a link is not unusual with respect to instruments or strategies typically employed by mainstream cognitive behavior therapists. (*Jasper, Emmelkamp, Paul 2015*)

To understand this phenomenon, we must consider the philosophical assumptions that underlie CBT. Mainstream CBT is not united by one philosophical or theoretical approach but instead is best described as a set of interventions linked in varying degrees to behavioral principles and cognitive theory. Nevertheless, the predominant philosophical perspective in traditional CBT (based on the cognitive model established by Beck et al., 1979) has been hypothetico-deductive cognitivism, a mechanistic approach whose underlying truth criterion is predictive verification. Hypothetico-deductive cognitivism models specific aspects of the normal functioning of the human mind and makes predictions on this basis regarding future behavior. (*Levin, Michael, Hildebrandt, Mikaela Lillis, Jason; Hayes, Steven 2023*)

However, the predictive truth criterion that characterizes this approach does not lend itself easily to practical application; hence, there is a disconnection between cognitive theory and practical application (e.g., CBT). For example, a typical model of cognitive functioning might involve one or more variables (e.g., cognitive schema), the existence of which has been hypothesized based on

the results of previous empirical work. In accordance with the mechanistic truth criterion, such a model might be reasonably useful at predicting relatively specific patterns of behavior based on relatively specific configurations of the cognitive system. However, the lack of emphasis on directly manipulable environmental variables and the specificity of the predictions mean that the model would be of little or no use for a clinician whose job is to influence a client's behavior. With respect to the development of new interventions, the clinician would then be left to rely more on clinical experience and common sense than on theory. *Mediavilla, Roberto 2023*)

Thus, although cognitive behavioral researchers have successfully demonstrated empirical support for a range of CBT-based intervention packages for particular disorders, including support for effective treatment components within these packages, such treatment packages are typically based not on a comprehensive bottom-up theoretical model of human cognition linked to basic behavior but rather on clinically derived considerations about how patients think (Hayes, Levin, Plumb, Boulanger, & Pistorello, 2023). Furthermore, even those theories that have been relatively successful in traditional CBT (e.g., Beck et al., 1979) have been specific in their scope and have tended to deemphasize aspects of context, such as overarching values. (*Öst, Lars-Göran 2024*).

Thus, traditional CBT does not lend itself readily to interventions to change behavior relevant to values, or even to measure such behavior. ACT, in contrast, although situated in the larger tradition of CBT, has its roots in an alternative set of philosophical assumptions that do allow both intervention and measurement of values-relevant behavior. ACT is closely linked to RFT, which is a behavior-analytic approach to language and cognition. Behavior analysis itself is rooted in the philosophical assumptions of functional contextualism, a form of scientific pragmatism in which truth is defined by the successful achievement of prediction and influence within the analytic domain (Hayes, Hayes, & Reese, 1988; Pepper, 1942). As a result, in RFT and ACT analyses, all concepts are explicitly linked to historical and situational contexts, because only contextual variables can be directly manipulated, thus allowing both prediction and influence (Hayes & Brownstein, 1986).

Hence, a key feature of the ACT-RFT approach to values that distinguishes it from many alternative approaches to values in the CBT tradition is an explicit focus on a bottom-up theoretical conception of this phenomenon that facilitates measurement and manipulation of contextual variables relevant to producing values-consistent patterns of action. In what follows, we examine the scientific detail of this bottom-up approach. (*Plumb, Jennifer, Stewart, Ian; Dahl, Joanne; Lundgren, Tobias 2023*).

Behavior Analysis and values

ACT is rooted in behavior analysis, which provides an empirically well-grounded and practically oriented system for prediction and influence of behavior, including value-relevant behavior. In behavior analysis, in contrast, terms are defined with sufficient functional precision for the purposes of analysis. (*Waltz, Thomas Hayes, Steven 2020*).

In presenting a functional definition of the term *value*, we start with a functional analysis of the conventional use of the term (Skinner, 1945). In the case of *value*, Leigland (2005) suggests that, with respect to the context of nonverbal animal behavior, the term might be emitted in the presence of operant reinforcement, especially the establishing operation (EO; e.g., Michael, 1982) in which the actual reinforcing effect of a particular reinforcer is manipulated. The classic example of an EO in the behavioral laboratory is food deprivation, which might be said to increase the reinforcing power or, to lay observers, the *value* of food. (Robb, Hank 2023)

EMPIRICAL REVIEW

Cheng, Darren et al. (2022) conducted a research, eighty-three reviews were selected and included 182 meta-analyses. Data were summarized visually and narratively using standardized mean differences with 95% confidence intervals as the primary outcome of interest. A large proportion of meta-analyses investigated fibromyalgia or mixed chronic pain, and psychological interventions were most commonly evaluated. Acceptance and commitment therapy for general chronic pain, and fluoxetine and web-based psychotherapy for fibromyalgia showed the most robust effects and can be prioritized for implementation in clinical practice. Exercise for arthritis, pharmacotherapy for neuropathic pain, self-regulatory psychotherapy for axial pain, and music therapy for general chronic pain showed large, significant effects, but estimates were derived from low- or critically low-quality reviews.

Gloster, Andrew T.; Walder, Noemi; Levin, Michael E.; Twohig, Michael P.; Karekla, Maria (2020). Explored on the efficacy of Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT) This paper reviews the meta-analytic evidence on ACT. The 20 included meta-analyses reported 100 controlled effect sizes across $n = 12,477$ participants. Controlled effect sizes were grouped by target conditions and comparison group. Results showed that ACT is efficacious for all conditions examined, including anxiety, depression, substance use, pain, and transdiagnostic groups. Results also showed that ACT was generally superior to inactive controls (e.g. waitlist, placebo), treatment as usual, and most active intervention conditions (excluding CBT). Weaknesses and areas for future development are discussed.

Cookson, Camilla; Luzon, Olga; Newland, John; Kingston, Jessica (2020) examined the Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT) proposes that cognitive fusion and experiential avoidance are inter-related processes underpinning distress. This study investigated whether worry, rumination, and stressful life events on the one hand and anxiety and depression on the other hand were mediated by cognitive fusion and experiential avoidance. A questionnaire design was conducted cross-sectional in a clinical sample (study 1; $N = 57$) and cross-sectional and longitudinally in a non-clinical student sample (study 2; $N = 106$ and $N = 97$ respectively). Participants completed measures of worry, rumination, stressful life events (predictors), cognitive fusion, experiential avoidance (mediators), anxiety, and depression (outcomes) at T1.

Anxiety and depression were measured again 6 weeks later. In the clinical sample, the bidirectional relationship between experiential avoidance and cognitive fusion accounted for a significant proportion of the association between rumination and depression, and stressful life events and

anxiety and depression. The association between worry and anxiety was mediated by cognitive fusion experiential avoidance only. In the non-clinical sample, in both cross-sectional and longitudinal analyses, cognitive fusion independently mediated the association between predictors and outcomes, as well as the experiential avoidance → cognitive fusion pathway. The bidirectional association between cognitive fusion and experiential avoidance was most predictive of distress in the clinical sample. In the non-clinical sample, cognitive fusion and the experiential avoidance → cognitive fusion pathway demonstrated more explanatory value. Given the cross-sectional nature of most of the data, the findings provide theoretical (as opposed to empirical) support for the models tested.

Ruiz, F. J. (2010) analyzes the general empirical evidence concerning Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT). In the first place, a brief description of the ACT philosophical and theoretical roots is presented. Subsequently, the most fundamental characteristics of the ACT model for psychological intervention are described. Then, a review of the correlational, experimental psychopathology and component, and outcome studies that are relevant for the ACT model empirical status is exposed. In general, the evidence regarding all these types of studies is very coherent and supports the ACT model. Specifically, experiential avoidance is found to be related with a wide range of psychological disorders and mediates the relation between different type of symptoms and psychological constructs; component studies are showing that acceptance-based protocols are usually more efficacious than other control-based protocols; outcome studies show the efficacy of ACT in a wide range of psychological problems and suggest that it is working through its hypothesized processes of change. However, the limitations of the actual empirical status of ACT are recognized and further research is emphasized.

Hayes, Steven C.; Luoma, Jason B.; Bond, Frank W.; Masuda, Akihiko; Lillis, Jason (2006) examine the model of psychopathology and treatment underlying Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT). ACT is unusual in that it is linked to a comprehensive active basic research program on the nature of human language and cognition (Relational Frame Theory), echoing back to an earlier era of behavior therapy in which clinical treatments were consciously based on basic behavioral principles. The evidence from correlational, component, process of change, and outcome comparisons relevant to the model are broadly supportive, but the literature is not mature and many questions have not yet been examined. What evidence is available suggests that ACT works through different processes than active treatment comparisons, including traditional Cognitive-Behavior Therapy (CBT). There are not enough well-controlled studies to conclude that ACT is generally more effective than other active treatments across the range of problems examined, but so far the data are promising.

Arch et al. (2012) conducted multilevel mediation analyses to assess the relationship of session-by-session changes in anxiety sensitivity and cognitive defusion with outcome measures at post-treatment. ACT showed borderline greater improvements than CBT in cognitive defusion whereas anxiety sensitivity was reduced in an equivalent degree in both conditions. Cognitive defusion significantly mediated worry, quality of life, behavioral avoidance and depression outcomes across both ACT and CBT. Anxiety sensitivity only had a mediating role in worry in both treatments.

Interestingly, cognitive defusion more strongly predicted worry reductions in CBT than in ACT. Overall, the data showed that ACT and CBT worked through similar mediation pathways. Finally, a moderation study (Wolitzky-Taylor et al., in press) found, on the one hand, that CBT outperformed ACT among participants with moderate levels of baseline anxiety sensitivity and among participants with no comorbid mood disorder. On the other hand, ACT outperformed CBT among participants with comorbid mood disorders. Two small RCTs have been conducted on test anxiety.

Zettle (2003) compared ACT versus systematic desensitization applied in 6 individual sessions for the treatment of mathematic anxiety (N= 24). Overall, results were slightly better for systematic desensitization at post-treatment, but the differences were reduced at follow-up. Participants did not show improvement on a mathematic test at post-treatment. This objective measure was selected for meta-analytic purposes ($g = .31$ favoring systematic desensitization). In a related study, Brown, Forman, Herbert, Hoffman, Yuen, and Goetter (2011) compared a protocol heavily based on ACT versus CT for text anxiety (N= 16). Both interventions were applied in a 2-hour group workshop. ACT produced improvements in performance (primary outcome), whereas CT participants exhibited a reduced performance. Two RCTs compared ACT versus CBT in worksite stress. (Mediavilla, Roberto 2023)

Bond and Bunce (2000) compared the effect of three 3-hour group session of ACT versus Innovation Promotion Program (IPP), a CBT package focused on problem solving that encourages people to identify and change stressors in their workplace. ACT showed better effects at post-treatment and at the 3-month follow-up in improving general mental health as measured by the GHQ (General Health Questionnaire; primary outcome for meta-analytic purposes). A mediation analysis presented in Hayes et al. (2006) indicated that decreases in experiential avoidance at post-treatment mediated the outcome results at the 3-month follow-up in ACT. Attempts to modify stressors and changes in dysfunctional attitudes did not mediate outcome results in IPP. Flaxman and Bond (2010) compared ACT versus a stress inoculation training (SIT) in working individuals with above average levels of distress (N= 74). The interventions consisted of two 3-hour group sessions. ACT and SIT reduced psychological distress to an equivalent degree across a 3-month assessment period. Mediation analyses indicated that the reduction of experiential avoidance mediated the outcome on the GHQ. However, reductions in dysfunctional attitudes did not mediate change in the SIT condition.

As Leigland (2005) indicates, “moving into the interpretation and analysis of human values naturally involves a considerable increase in complexity, because verbal contingencies are involved in any distinctively human behavioral phenomenon”. He then describes a conception of human values that corresponds closely to the ACT-RFT approach. Although human values involve an increase in complexity, the idea of the EO is still relevant because when someone says that he or she values someone or something that statement refers to the effectiveness of that person or thing as a reinforcer for their behavior. The difference is that in this case the EO is verbal, a

phenomenon that can in turn be analyzed as a kind of rule-governed behavior and more specifically as an augmental verbal contingency (Zettle & Hayes, 1982).

According to Zettle and Hayes (1982), there are two types of augmental rules, formative and motivative. Formative augmental rules establish a stimulus as reinforcing or punishing. For example, the statement “These tickets are worth money” establishes the tickets to which it refers as reinforcing or valuable. Motivative augmental rules temporarily alter the effectiveness of a previously established consequence. For example, the realization that “I love my job” may, at least temporarily, make job-relevant activity even more reinforcing than before. There is now established empirical support for both these forms of augmental rule following (Hayes, Kohlenberg, & Hayes, 1991; Ju & Hayes, 2008; Whelan & Barnes-Holmes, 2004).

Leigland (2005) suggests that in the case of augmental rule following, “reinforcement may be a derived function established through participation in a network of relations among arbitrary stimuli” (p. 137). This is the contention of RFT, which explains verbal behavior, including augmental rule following, as a form of operant behavior and thus acts as a critical theoretical link to explain the exact difference between nonverbal and verbal forms of the EO. In what follows, RFT will be briefly outlined before we consider the ACT-RFT definition of values in detail.

(Okoro 2024) explore the effect of cognitive behavior therapy in adolescents with Mythomania disorder in Ehime Mbanjo Local Government of Imo State. Mythomania refers to a compulsive tendency to lie and deceive others. A literature search was conducted using the CINAHL and MEDLINE databases. The database search occurred during the month of January 2024. The article comprehensively summarizes the theoretical basis of CBT in improving Mythomania disorder, its application in managing symptoms and improving social function, as well as research progress in the field. There were inconsistencies in the research results on CBT, but overall, psychological intervention combined with drug treatment is more effective than conventional treatment alone. The research found that if social function training can be added at the same time, it is believed that it will have better effects on clinical treatment and can maintain long-lasting effectiveness. Only in this way can adolescents truly understand and recognize the disease, improve treatment compliance, and ultimately achieve the goal of improving the disorder and have quality of life. Therapists or psychologists use CBT for adolescents to help them become aware of irrational or negative thinking so they can see situations clearly, process them, and respond to them in healthy ways. CBT intervention for adolescents can be a powerful part of an integrated treatment plan for adolescent mental health disorders.

METHODOLOGY

The study evaluated the impact of acceptance and commitment therapy (ACT) on older adults with obsessive compulsive disorder (OCD) in Abuja metropolitan area Nigeria. The study ascertain the effectiveness of this therapy on reducing the frequency of compulsions, intensity of obsessive

symptoms, depression, anxiety and increased willingness to have obsessions was measured. A single case-study design with baseline design was used in this study. The results were analyzed not only by descriptive format. All 5 old adult showed very high reduction in period of the therapy compared to the baseline period and this reduction was maintained with respect to all 5 Old adults during the follow up period. The average of first client’s compulsions within 4 weeks of baseline was 14.87 and its standard deviation was 0.82. These results during 10 treatment weeks were 3.98 and 3.53 respectively. Namely, a considerable reduction was observed in the frequency of compulsions and this reduction continued until one month after the therapy; namely, within four follow-up weeks, the average of compulsions was 2.02 with standard deviation of 0.86. The second client did not show much reduction with average of 19.57 and standard deviation of 1.72. During the baseline period, the client did not have much reduction after beginning of therapy; however, she demonstrated a significant reduction from the third week (SD=5.47, M=4.94). This reduction was also continued during the follow-up period (SD=0.64, M=1.77). The average of the third client during baseline was 7.85 with 0.68 of standard deviation.

There is a significant difference between the groups treated with ACT and those treated as usual, on every domain of thought control questionnaire (TCQ) -- distraction (t = 9.07), social control (t = 11.13), worry (t = 11.93), punishment (t = 16.78), and re-appraisal (t = 16.47). Significance is also seen in the thought and action fusion in the moral domain (t = 16.22), the likelihood domain (t = 16.49), and others (t = 9.23).

Table 1. Characteristics of included studies.

Research Evidence on ACT for OCD

To date, there are around 300 RCTs for ACT, analyzing various conditions, and few have found ACT to be an effective treatment for OCD. Several meta-analyses have found optimistic effect sizes for ACT in treating various mental illnesses. Currently, nine RCTs exploring the role of ACT for OCD have been conducted.

Risks of Bias of Included Studies

Figure 2 describe the analysis of the risks of bias. No study was entirely evaluated as bearing a low risk of bias through all the study areas. The random sequence generation and adequately concealed allocation had a low risk (12 studies or 90%). A few studies did not state if blinding techniques were used, perhaps because the authors presumed that blinding was not viable due to the intervention’s quality. Regarding the blinding of participants and personnel, 12 studies were reported to have low risks and 1 study was reported to have unclear and high risks.

Figure 2. Risk of bias graph: review authors' judgments about each risk of bias item presented as percentages across all included studies.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results suggested the significant decreases in all measures in five older patients and these results maintained at 1-month follow up. Process of treatment and results from this study suggest that Acceptance and Commitment Therapy can be effective intervention for difficult thoughts, feelings, and behaviors seen in OCD. The results of meta-analysis on the effect of ACT alone showed that ACT had a better effect on OCD than other treatment methods ($MD = -3.76$, $Z = 4.41$, $P \leq 0.05$). Meta-analysis results of ACT combined SSRIs therapy showed that ACT combined therapy was better than SSRIs alone ($MD = 7.18$, $Z = 6.59$, $P \leq 0.05$). The study concluded that acceptance commitment therapy can effectively treat OCD. The findings of the study indicate that ACT is a productive method for patients with OCD as it encourages the patient to accept and integrate their lived experiences, challenges effective responses, and recognizes and eliminates the controlling dimensions.

CONCLUSION

The comprehensive analysis of the studies led to various conclusions. In their meta-analysis and systematic review, found that ACT is "possibly efficacious" in treating OCD. In the study, the ACT is probably effective in treating OCD on older adults. There is a higher plausibility because more RCTs and other study designs have been performed to acknowledge the growing presence of ACT in the mental health domain. In addition, the studies, provides evidence for the effectiveness of ACT. Precisely, it includes studies with high methodological rigors. Moreover, in line with systematic review, evidence for using ACT in OCD was drawn not only from RCTs but also from case series and case studies. These studies had evident drawbacks, such as a small sample size or subjective characteristics of the narratives. However, the affirmative results of this current meta-analysis were essential in positing ACT as a conceivable intervention for acceptance and

commitment therapy (act) on older adults with obsessive compulsive disorder (OCD) in Abuja metropolitan area Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings it was recommended that the present study indicate that ACT is a productive method for patients with OCD as it encourages the patient to accept and integrate their lived experiences, challenges effective responses, and recognizes and eliminates the controlling dimensions. The study acknowledge the plausibility of ACT in treating OCD and improving its symptoms for the clinical population. ACT can also be an adjunct therapy for other well-established treatments. It also favors targeting psychological inflexibility.

Results suggested the significant decreases in all measures in five older patients and these results maintained at 1-month follow up. Process of treatment and results from this study suggest that Acceptance and Commitment Therapy can be effective intervention for difficult thoughts, feelings, and behaviors seen in the impact of acceptance and commitment therapy (ACT) on older adults with obsessive compulsive disorder (OCD) in Abuja metropolitan area Nigeria.

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External links

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